

Is Education a Tool for Empowerment?

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Abstract

Women education in India has a major preoccupation of both the government and civil society as educated women can play a very important role in the development of the country. Education is milestone of women empowerment because it enables them to responds to the challenges, to confront their traditional role and change their life. So that we can't neglect the importance of education in reference to women empowerment and India poised to becoming superpower in recent years. Education of women is the most powerful tool to change the position in society. Women education in India has been a need of the hour, as education is a foundation stone for the empowerment of woman.

Education also brings a reduction in inequalities and functions as a means of improving their status within the family and develops the concept of participation.

Keywords:

Education, preoccupation, milestone, empowerment, participation

Introduction

As we turn back the pages of human development, women have played a vital role in the history making as men. In fact higher status for women through employment and work performed by them in a society is a significant indicator of a nation's overall progress. Mahakvi Bharathi, the pioneer of modern thought has worked a lot for women empowerment and for making her place in the society a vital one. His poems and works are capable of creating sense of general awareness of values whenever they are recalled. "Viduthalikku Magalir", "Penmai Vaazhagavendru", "Om Shakthi Shakthi", "Kummiyadi" are a few written by him for women empowerment. Apart from empowerment, his songs also

contributed a lot, spreading messages of rights, liberation, boldness, briskness, alertness, self-discipline, awareness, ability and leadership qualities of women.

What so ever done for empowering women and up bringing her status in the society, at times women imposes upon themselves a restriction which prevents them from being bold, taking initiative, going ahead and leading a team. This conceptual paper tries to throw light upon women empowerment by using education as a tool and also highlights upon the aspect that, mere education alone can't empower women as a whole

Importance of women education

“If you educate a man you educate an individual, however, if you educate a woman you educate a whole family. Women empowered means mother India empowered”. PT. JAWAHARLAL NEHRU. Women education in India plays a very important role in the overall development of the country. It not only helps in the development of half of the human resources, but in improving the quality of life at home and outside.¹ If it is said that education is the key to all problems, then it won't be improper. Thinkers have given a number of definitions of education but out of these definitions, the most important definition is that which was put forth by M. Phule. According to M. Phule, "Education is that which demonstrates the difference between what is good and what is evil". If we consider the above definition, we come to know that whatever revolutions that have taken place in our history, education is at the base of them.² Education means modification of behaviour in every aspect, such as mentality, outlook, attitude etc. Educated women not only tend to promote education of their girl children, but also can provide better guidance to all their children. Moreover educated women can also help in the reduction of infant mortality rate and growth of the population. **Obstacles:** Gender discrimination still persists in India and lot more needs to be done in the field of women's education in India. The gap in the male-female literacy rate is just a simple indicator. While the male literary rate is more than 82.14% and the female literacy rate is just 65.46%.(b). the women were consider only house wife and better to be live in the house.¹

Women Empowerment & Education

¹ <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1081705.pdf>

The word „empower“ means to bestow power. This power has made women independent, by paving way to various opportunities. According to United Nations Development Programme (1994), empowerment is process which enables individuals or social groups to change balances of power in social, economic and political relations in society. It is also used to represent self-responsibility and self- determination. The economic growth of a country is positively affected by empowering a woman.

“If you want something said, ask a man; if you want something done, ask a woman.”

-Margaret Thatcher

Women Empowerment means moving from enforced powerlessness to a position of power and education plays a vital role in it. It is an essential means of empowering women with knowledge, skills and self-confidence which is required to fully participate in her overall development. Education is important for everyone but it is a critical area of empowerment for women. This is not only because women’s education is an entry point to many opportunities but also because a woman’s educational achievements have a positive rippling effect within the family and also across generations.

Education is a key factor for women empowerment prosperity, development and welfare. The status of women in a complex society like India is not uniform. The dynamics of the future call for knowledge leadership. India today can boost of a large educated manpower, which is crucial for the socio-economic growth of any nation. It also brings a reduction in inequalities and functions as a means of improving their status within the family. Education is much more than reading and writing. It is an essential investment for countries to make their futures, a crucial factor in reducing poverty and achieving an economic status in the society. Without the active participation of women in national activities, the social, economic or political progress of a country will deteriorate and become stagnant.

Equal Opportunities for Sustainable Development

Education is a vital aspect for empowering women and her development. It is an essential means to empower her with knowledge, skills and self-confidence so as to effectively contribute in the development of our economy. Sustainable development is only possible when women and men have equal opportunities to prove themselves. Women experience many inequalities in the day-to-day life. There are many structural barriers in the society

which are obstacles to women's economic, political and sustainable empowerment. If equal opportunities are given, women can definitely prove her in every scenario of life and situation.

Is Education Enough for Empowerment?

Every year we celebrate the International Women's Day to make sure that people know the importance of women and the day-to-day challenges they face. People deliver big speeches on the day to celebrate womanhood. The day is led by catchy cries and the campaign rests on the notion that if you invest in a woman, she will do the rest, pulling herself, her family, her community and her country, out of all evils. On this day people use the word "empowerment" frequently, but actually it is very tough to define and measure. Few of them say that education is the ultimate thing to empower a woman, but some say that it is attained only when she is in an earning capacity. Even though there were and are, many contributors for women empowerment, women are not actually empowered in the real sense.

There are women who are well educated and are in a good earning capacity but are not empowered. The reason being that she is in some way by self-lowers her own status out of love, affection and respect towards the male characters in the society.

Today the words empower has become a synonym to education. But actually it is not such in reality. Education even though a vital aspect, may not be considered as a silver bullet towards women empowerment. Building big educational institutions doesn't build a pathway to empowerment. Women must also be emotionally empowered to exploit the opportunities. She must be strong enough to face and overcome all the challenges on her way towards success. Only then she can enjoy the status of being an empowered woman as a whole.

Conclusion

Women have the potential to change their own economic status but yet her contributions are unrecognized and her work is undervalued. Unequal opportunities between women and men hamper women's ability to uplift her-self in life. Education is considered as a powerful tool for changing a women's position in society to empower her status. The importance of education as a tool of empowerment is undeniable. Certainly, it's a true fact that big

improvements have been made for women education but mere enrolment alone doesn't provide equal empowerment as men in the society. Women should also have a strong emotional withstand in every aspect of the society to attain the status she actually deserves.

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